

Strategic Management of Human Resources in light of Technological changes

Al-Mafrachi, Mustafa Saad; Aboura, Enas Hussein & Abed, Hanaa Najm

Abstract

The study begins with four hypotheses, the first one relates to the significance of managing human resources within the organization; the second one relates to information, which has become the most important source from which human resources derive their strength. The fourth hypothesis concerns the contribution to the adaptation and adaptation of technological changes of the strategic human resources management. This study sought to highlight the role of strategic human resources management in view of technological changes as institutions adapt to technological changes. A number of results have been found, including: The strategy on human resources is part and parcel of the strategy of the organization. Thus, the human resources management functions and practices are all in the service of other strategies of departments. The profound change in people in organizations because of the transition from people management to human resources management, taking the human element into consideration as an important factor in the organization and calling for the optimum administration of human resources in various levels and activities.

IJSB

Accepted 14 July 2021
Published 20 July 2021
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5115472

Keywords: *human resources, strategic management, technological changes, management function, technological changes.*

About Author (s)

Al-Mafrachi, Mustafa Saad (corresponding author), The Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Bucharest, Romania. Email: mustafa3.saad@gmail.com

Aboura, Enas Hussein, The Bucharest University Of Economic Studies, Bucharest, Romania

Abed, Hanaa Najm, University of Agriculture and Veterinary Medicine, Bucharest, Romania.

1. introduction:

Institutions possess many resources that enable them to achieve a competitive advantage and reach their desired goals, and these resources can be classified into: material, human, and organizational resources, which are under the control of management and through which a competitive advantage can be achieved. HR the executives is quite possibly the most significant and delicate useful offices in the association, as it manages the main component of creation and the most weak assets of the association to be influenced by inner natural changes of the climate of the establishment, outside ecological changes and what is implied by general society and private climate. The association, totally HR the executives, can settle on many trustworthy choices that empower it to confront ecological difficulties and guarantee coherence and endurance. Where HR got perhaps the main serious variables in the accomplishment of the association, which gave it an essential measurement in its administration, which made the HR work shift from its administration system to its essential job in light of the fact that the conventional job of HR is not, at this point adequate to accomplish the goals of the organization and this is the thing that necessary its administration as indicated by an essential viewpoint. It pays to activate the energies and exercises of HR to assist the association with accomplishing its objectives.

Considering the progressions and changes that the world is seeing in different parts of contemporary life, numerous beneficial and monetary foundations experience the ill effects of issues of excess or deficiency at certain occasions from HR in different fields of work, and keeping in mind that specific divisions or areas in some different organizations whine about the expansion in the quantity of people Its real need. We track down that different offices or segments experience the ill effects of work pressing factor and failure to accomplish their objectives because of their restricted HR. There is no uncertainty that the essential administration of HR is considered among the main contemporary practices that draw the approach of managing the drawn out association with the human component, and all issue identified with it identified with his profession in his working environment, and in accordance with the acts of the overall establishment's methodology, conditions and mission. The HR technique has become an essential piece of the methodologies of current associations, as the capacities and practices of HR the executives serve the procedures of different divisions.

Figure number: (1). The role of human resource management in the organization

Source: whatishumanresource.com¹

¹ Human Resource Management, whatishumanresource.com, Available at: <http://www.whatishumanresource.com/human-resource-management>

The above model (Figure 1) illustrates the purpose of managing human resources in organizations in light of technological development, as the model indicates that the purpose of this department is to deal with employees to perform their jobs in the organization (duties and responsibilities), in addition to providing them with training, taking care of them, and achieving Their safety.

2. Methodological framework for the study:

2.1. The problem of the study:

2.2. Since the essential administration of HR adds to the establishments' transformation to mechanical changes, the human asset the executives is likewise among the divisions influenced by the innovative upheaval, as the mechanical upset incredibly affected the administration of HR with its different systems in the foundation, which is the primary source from which these offices determine Other recognized proficient abilities. **As needs be, the tricky of this investigation rotates around the accompanying inquiry: What is the part of vital administration of HR considering mechanical changes?**

2.3. Study hypotheses:

In achieving its objectives, the study starts from the following assumptions:

- **The first hypothesis:** human resource management is an important function and pillar of the basic pillars upon which any institution is based.
- **The second hypothesis:** Information has become the most important source from which the human resource derives its power.
- **The third hypothesis:** Various technological changes have affected the management of human resources and provided them with advanced information systems for their development and development.
- **The fourth hypothesis:** The strategic management of human resources contributes to institutions achieving adaptation and adaptation to technological changes.

2.4. Objectives of the study:

This study aims to:

- A. Shedding light on the strategic management system for human resources that ensures the institutions achieve continuity and long-term goals.
- B. Highlighting the role of technological variables in developing the quality and skills of human resources, making them compatible with the developments of the information age.
- C. Highlighting the importance of institutions strengthening their information technology infrastructure to achieve the maximum possible benefit in the field of human resources management.

2.5. Study concepts:

2.5.1. Strategic management:

According to Strick Land and Thompson, strategic management is the process by which managers can establish a long-term direction for the organization, define its goals and develop strategies, with the aim of achieving these goals in light of the relevant internal variables².

² Michael Armstrong, *Armstrong's Handbook of Management and Leadership: Developing Effective People Skills for Better Leadership and Management*, Philadelphia: Kogan Page, (3rd edition), 2012, P: 25

As for Vincz and Higgins, strategic management is the administrative currency that aims to fulfill the mission of the organization by managing and directing the institution's relationship with its environment³.

It is evident from the above that: Strategic management is the management of the expected relationships between institutions and their external environment, so that this perception clarifies the processes that must be performed in the long and medium term in order for the institutions to go to their goals and reach the goals they must achieve.

2.5.2. Human Resource Management:

Human resources management is defined as the administrative activity related to identifying the organization's needs of the workforce and providing them with the preparation and specific competencies and coordinating the utilization of this human resource with the highest possible efficiency⁴. According to another definition, human resource management is a law or system that defines the methods and organization of the treatment of individuals working in the organization so that they can achieve themselves and also the optimal use of their capabilities and capabilities to achieve the highest productivity⁵.

Based on the foregoing, it becomes clear that: Human resources management represents one of the important functions in institutions, which is specialized in managing personnel affairs in the organization in order to put the right person in the right place in order to achieve the objectives of the institution and ensure its survival and continuity.

2.5.3. Strategic management of human resources:

One of the definitions of this concept indicates that it means the decision-making process related to the human resources system that works to achieve the adaptation of the human resources system to the surrounding environmental conditions and to support the organization's strategies and achieving its goals⁶.

For his part, Rand Scholar defines strategic human resource management as a department that aims to achieve integration between human resource management and enterprise strategy⁷.

From the above, it can be said that: Strategic management of human resources is a group of coordinated actions and actions aimed at integrating the organizational environment, and this concept includes the strategic participation of human resources in the formation, preparation and implementation of the business strategy as a whole.

3. The theoretical framework of the study:

3.1. Fundamentals about strategic management:

³ Akinyele Samuel Taiwo Fasogbon Olufunke Idunnu, Impact of Strategic Planning on Organizational Performance and Survival, Research Journal of Business Management, 1: 62-71. 2007, P: 64. Available at: <https://scialert.net/abstract/?doi=rjbm.2007.62.71>

⁴ Chew, Eng K.Gottschalk, Petter, Information Technology Strategy and Management: Best Practices: Best Practices, Pennsylvania: IGI Global, 2009, P: 89

⁵ Birdir, Kemal, Birdir, Sevda, Dalgic, Ali, Toksoz, Derya, Impact of ICTs on Event Management and Marketing, Pennsylvania: IGI Global, 2020, P: 95

⁶ Catherine Bailey, David Mankin, Clare Kelliher, Strategic Human Resource Management, Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2018, P: 51

⁷ Richard Regis, Strategic Human Resource Management and Development, New Delhi: Excel Books, 2008, P: 80

The topic of strategic management is one of the vital topics in contemporary managerial thought due to its interest in decisions related to resource allocation and building relationships in the internal and external environment in the long run, with a focus on studying and analyzing products and markets, and researching approaches to dealing with competitors, in a way that achieves the long-term goals and objectives of institutions⁸.

3.1.1. Importance of strategic management:

Exploration and studies demonstrate that the selection of vital administration by the administration of the foundation assists it with explaining the future vision of the work and draw a future picture that the association can reach, and furthermore assists it with cooperating in the drawn out climate, and this communication thusly makes the association ready to manage conditions and advancements and enables it to adjust With variations⁹. The institution's adoption of strategic management enables it to adopt new creative ideas that contribute to developing capabilities that generate a desire to develop the institution's reality through continuous and positive changes, and at the same time lead to strengthening the institution's competitive position and making it capable of building capabilities that contribute to strengthening this center and achieving positive results¹⁰. The essential administration of the establishment gives a particular premise to distinguishing the requirements for change, featuring these requirements for every authoritative level, as well as assisting with survey change as a chance and not a danger, just as laying logical and sound establishments for dispensing assets and abilities, particularly uncommon ones, on the different specialty units and utilitarian exercises in the association, just as It additionally addresses a structure for improving administration practice through the coordination and control of exercises or their oversight¹¹.

3.1.2. Levels and processes of strategic management:

Strategic management has three levels and passes through three stages.

3.1.3. As for the levels of strategic management, they are¹²:

The strategic management of the institution: At this level, the essential administration is associated with the way toward arranging all exercises identified with figuring the mission of the organization, deciding its essential objectives, looking for the fundamental assets, and forming the essential arrangement considering dissecting the interior climate of the foundation, and the outside climate.

Strategic management at the level of strategic business units: The essential administration at this level is straightforwardly liable for arranging and coordinating every one of the exercises of the unit's essential arrangement and taking the fundamental choices for its execution.

Strategic management at the functional level: since the essential specialty units typically comprise of subsystems: the creation work, individuals, showcasing, monetary undertakings, and so forth, so it was vital for the association to have clear techniques for these useful frameworks, at the end of the day there is an essential arrangement Each essential

⁸ Jaimin H Trivedi, Fundamentals Of Strategic Planning And Development, Navamuvada: Red Unicorn Publishing Pvt, Ltd, 2019, Pp: 8 - 9

⁹ Paul W. Dobson, Ken Starkey, John Richards, Strategic Management: Issues and Cases, Wiley.com, 2009, P: 121

¹⁰ R. SRINIVASAN, STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT: THE INDIAN CONTEXT, New Delhi: PHI Learning Pvt. Ltd, 2014, P: 3

¹¹ Tan, Albert Wee Kwan, Theodorou, Petros, Strategic Information Technology and Portfolio Management, Pennsylvania: IGI Global, 2009, P: 315

¹² Graham Hubbard, John Rice, Peter Galvin, Strategic Management, Pearson Australia, 2014, P: 21

arrangement embraces the way toward assessing the strategies, projects and methods for executing each work without delving into the subtleties of direct management of the day by day exercises of these positions.

3.1.4. As for the stages of strategic management processes, they are¹³:

The design stage: It is likewise called the essential arranging stage, and this stage incorporates characterizing the mission of the association, characterizing long haul objectives and targets, examining the outer and inside climate and recognizing the essential hole.

Implementation stage: This stage plans to carry out the techniques that have been planned, and incorporates defining transient objectives, forming approaches, assigning material and HR and circulating them among spending choices, and it additionally requires setting up the foundation from within, including the alteration of the hierarchical design and the reallocation of forces and duties.

Evaluation stage: Procedures are dependent upon an assessment cycle to see their reasonableness with the progressions that happen in the inward and outside climate, and this requires contrasting the genuine outcomes and the normal objectives and finding deviations that might be in the plan or execution period of the technique.

3.2. The main functions of human resources management:

The human resources department has tasks like any other department, it has an administrative function that is represented in the other departments of the organization, and a second specialized job that distinguishes it from other departments¹⁴.

3.2.1. As for the administrative function of human resources management, it is¹⁵:

The planning function

The arranging capacity is worried about deciding the association's necessities of HR, as far as amount and quality, which guarantee the accomplishment of the association's objectives.

The function of organization: With the improvement of the capacity of people in the association and the formation of a free office for it that plans, creates approaches and attracts programs identified with people through tracking down the proper association, the capacity of association for this situation partitions and characterizes the obligations, duties and specialists among people and characterizes the connections that tight spot these obligations.

The guidance function: it implies coordinating the endeavors of people towards accomplishing the objectives of the association, and the point of this work is to encourage people to work with complete fulfillment and viability.

Control function: The control interaction is an authoritative capacity identified with getting sorted out exercises and planning between them as indicated by the particular work plan dependent on the examination of the destinations or the fundamental exercises of the association to guarantee the execution of the overall arrangement of the foundation with high proficiency.

¹³ Robert S. Kaplan, David P. Norton, *The Execution Premium: Linking Strategy to Operations for Competitive Advantage*, Harvard: Harvard Business School Press, 2008, P: 283

¹⁴ Tapomoy Deb, *Managing Human Resource And Industrial Relations*, New Delhi: Excel Books, 2009, P: 60

¹⁵ J. Barton Cunningham, *Strategic Human Resource Management in the Public Arena: A Managerial Perspective*, London: Macmillan International Higher Education, 2016, Pp: 20: 22

3.2.2. With regard to the specialized functions of human resources management, they are¹⁶:

The function of attracting human resources: It is considered the first specialized job for human resources management and is concerned with determining the institution's needs of human resources, both quantitatively and qualitatively, in order to ensure the achievement of the organization's objectives.

Staff training and development function: After the foundation gets the fundamental HR in amount and quality in accordance with the necessities of the organization's goals, their abilities should be ceaselessly evolved to raise the degree of proficiency and improve execution, and this is done through constant preparing to guarantee the wellbeing of the work execution. This capacity is viewed as one of the essential capacities that guarantee that the organization keeps on confronting innovative advancements in working techniques and creation devices.

The compensation or reward function: The remuneration or award work is one of the significant elements of HR the executives, and this work is worried about deciding a reasonable compensation or prize construction in accordance with the exertion made by the labor force in the association.

Manpower Care and Maintenance Job: This position is worried about the consideration and support of labor by giving wellbeing, social, sporting and social consideration, just as care from departing administration.

3.2.3. Importance and objectives of human resources management:

Human resources management is very important in organizations through its role in achieving their goals¹⁷.

3.2.4. As for the importance of human resources management, it is¹⁸:

Having specialized expertise in human resources management that is able and qualified to attract the best employees to fill vacant positions increases the productivity of the institution and enhances its economic position and profits in the long run. The adoption of the Human Resources Department of the development and training programs for the employees of the organization contributes to providing a suitable organizational climate for work, and this would motivate the employees and push them to exert more of their capabilities as a result of their job satisfaction and thus increase the effectiveness of the organization as a whole. Human resource management saves many potential costs resulting from the rapid turnover of work through correct and fair treatment of potential problems in the areas of selecting and appointing employees and evaluating their performance.

3.2.5. On the objectives of human resources management, they are¹⁹:

Social goals: through the application of community goals to employ individuals according to their capabilities, allowing community development and growth in accordance with labor and labor legislation and laws, and creating an appropriate climate to protect them from dangers.

¹⁶ Vida Gulbinas Scarpello, *The Handbook of Human Resource Management Education: Promoting an Effective and Efficient Curriculum*, California: SAGE Publications, 2007, P: 87 - 88

¹⁷ Ramesh Kumar Miryala, *Trends, Challenges & Innovations in Management*, Hyderabad: Zenon academic publishing, 2015, P: 27

¹⁸ Edward Lawler, *Effective Human Resource Management: A Global Analysis*, California: Stanford University Press, 2012, Pp: 110 - 111

¹⁹ Gurpreet Randhawa, *Human Resource Management*, New Delhi: Atlantic Publishing, 2007, Pp: 2 - 3

Organizational objectives: That the HR office play out its capacity in a reasonable way with the remainder of the parts of the association and give exhortation and direction in regards to the issues of people in the association.

Functional goals: through the human resources department performing the special functions related to the personnel working in the organization according to its need.

Humanitarian goals: by satisfying the desires and needs of the individuals working in the organization, being an important element in the production process.

3.3. Strategic management of human resources:

The essential administration of HR is among the main contemporary practices that draw the arrangement of managing the drawn out association with the human component and all issue identified with it identified with his vocation in his working environment and in accordance with the acts of the overall association's procedure, conditions and mission²⁰.

3.3.1. The trend towards strategic human resources departments:

HR technique is a vital piece of the association's procedure, in this manner the capacities and practices of human asset the board all work in the help of other offices' systems²¹.

The profound transformations that included human behavior in organizations due to the shift from managing people to managing human resources, which took into account the human element as an important factor in the organization, urged the management of human resources in an optimal manner in various levels and activities. Other transformations were also known as the transition from management Human resources in its old concept to the strategic management of human resources in its modern concept in order to adapt individuals to the changing internal and external environment²².

3.3.2. Components and importance of strategic human resource management:

Strategic management of human resources represents a sequential process that aims to integrate human resources practices with the operations of the organization in order to achieve the competitive advantage of the organization.

3.3.3. The following are the components of strategic human resources management²³:

Designs and organizational structures: are those that are highly distinctive, and this is achieved through effective human resources planning, job standard conditions, job analysis and description, decision-making style and market orientation.

Selection and Recruitment: Selection criteria include strategic planning, and the selection of managers and leaders.

Training and development: includes types of internal and external training, needs identification and training return measurement.

²⁰ David Farnham, Human Resource Management in Context: Insights, Strategy and Solutions, London: Kogan Page Publishers, 2015, P; 120

²¹ Ashok Chanda, Jie Shen, HRM Strategic Integration and Organizational Performance, California: SAGE Publications Ltd, 2009, P: 58

²² Management Association, Information Resources, Research Anthology on Digital Transformation, Organizational Change, and the Impact of Remote Work, California: IGI Global, 2020, P: 827

²³ Farid Al-Najjar, Strategic Management for Human Resources, Alexandria: University House, 2006, pp. 92-93

Compensation system: includes types of individual and group incentives, negative and positive, material and moral, methods of wage payment, and other material and moral compensation.

Productivity improvement programs: It includes applications of total quality management and measurement of total quality results in sources, inputs, processes and results, environmental uses, management and continuous improvements, and development comparisons with competitors.

Labor relations: includes the degree of commitment to apply labor laws, social insurance, pensions, treatment and medicine, and achieving job satisfaction.

Occupational health competency: includes applications of occupational safety, prevention of accidents, and relief of work stress and diseases.

3.3.4. With regard to the importance of strategic management of human resources, it is as follows:

The importance of strategic management is evident in economic institutions due to the internal environment challenges such as²⁴:

Low individual satisfaction with the wages and benefits granted to the inability of the enterprise to meet its essential needs.

Professional competencies think about emigration due to the great temptations.

The increasing demand for labor to involve them in the decision-making process.

Its importance also appears due to the challenges of the external environment, including²⁵:

- Rapid development of products and services.
- The revolution in technology and communication and the information provided by it has cast a shadow over the quality of products and the evaluation of services.

4. Conclusion:

HR the board is quite possibly the main useful divisions in the organization and the most sensitive, as it deals with the most important element of production and the most vulnerable resources of the organization to be affected by internal environmental changes of the organization's environment, and external environmental changes that are meant by the public and private environment. HR have gotten quite possibly the main serious variables in the accomplishment of the association, which gave it an essential measurement in its administration, which made the HR work shift from its administration structure to its essential job in light of the fact that the customary part of HR is not, at this point adequate to accomplish the destinations of the establishment and this is the thing that necessary its administration as indicated by an essential viewpoint. Vital administration of HR is among the main contemporary practices that draw a strategy of managing the association for long haul with the human component.

²⁴ Abou-Zeid El-Sayed, Knowledge Management and Business Strategies: Theoretical Frameworks and Empirical Research: Theoretical Frameworks and Empirical Research, Pennsylvania: IGI Global, 2007, P: 41

²⁵ Zhao Fang, Information Technology Entrepreneurship and Innovation, Pennsylvania: IGI Global, 2008, P: 92

The HR technique has become a fundamental piece of the methodologies of current associations, as the capacities and practices of HR the board serve the systems of different offices. Strategic management is the management of the expected relationships between institutions and their external environment, so that this visualization clarifies the processes that must be performed in the long and medium term in order for institutions to go to their goals and reach the goals they must achieve. HR the board addresses one of the significant capacities in foundations, which is represented considerable authority in overseeing faculty issues in the association to place the opportune individual in the perfect spot to accomplish the destinations of the organization and guarantee its endurance and coherence. Vital administration of HR is a gathering of composed activities and activities focused on the incorporation of the hierarchical climate, and this idea remembers the essential support of HR for the development, planning and execution of the business technique all in all.

References:

1. Taiwo, A. S., & Idunnu, F. O. (2007). Impact of Strategic Planning on Organizational. *Research Journal of Business Management*, 1(1), 62-71.
2. Al-Najjar, F. (2006). *Strategic Management for Human Resources*. Alexandria: University House.
3. Armstrong, M. (2012). *Armstrong's handbook of management and leadership: developing effective people skills for better leadership and management*. Kogan Page Publishers.
4. Birdir, Kemal, Birdir, Sevda, Dalgic, Ali, Toksoz, Derya. (2020). *Impact of ICTs on Event Management and Marketing*. Pennsylvania: IGI Global.
5. Bailey, C., Mankin, D., Kelliher, C., & Garavan, T. (2018). *Strategic human resource management*. Oxford University Press.
6. Chew, E. K., & Gottschalk, P. (Eds.). (2009). *Information Technology Strategy and Management: Best Practices: Best Practices*. IGI Global.
7. Cunningham, J. B. (2016). *Strategic human resource management in the public arena: A managerial perspective*. Macmillan International Higher Education.
8. Deb, T. (2009). *Managing human resource and industrial relations*. Excel Books India.
9. Abou-Zeid, E. S. (Ed.). (2007). *Knowledge Management and Business Strategies: Theoretical Frameworks and Empirical Research: Theoretical Frameworks and Empirical Research*. IGI Global.
10. Fang, Z. (2008). *Information Technology Entrepreneurship and Innovation*. Pennsylvania: IGI Global.
11. Farnham, D. (2015). *Human resource management in context: Insights, strategy and solutions*. Kogan Page Publishers.
12. Graham Hubbard, . R. (2014). *Strategic Management*. Pearson Australia.
13. Lawler, E. (2012). *Effective Human Resource Management: A Global Analysis*. California: Stanford University Press.
14. Management Association, Information Resources. (2020). *Research Anthology on Digital Transformation, Organizational Change, and the Impact of Remote Work*. California: IGI Global.
15. Miryala, R. K. (2015). *Trends, Challenges & Innovations in Management*. Hyderabad: Zenon academic publishing.
16. Paul W. Dobson, Ken Starkey, John Richards. (2009). *Strategic Management: Issues and Cases*. Wiley.com.
17. Randhawa, G. (2007). *Human Resource Management*. New Delhi: Atlantic Publishing.
18. Regis, R. (2008). *Strategic Human Resource Management and Development*. New Delhi: Excel Books.

19. Robert S. Kaplan, David P. Norton. (2008). *The Execution Premium: Linking Strategy to Operations for Competitive Advantage*. Harvard: Harvard Business School Press.
20. Scarpello, V. G. (2007). *The Handbook of Human Resource Management Education: Promoting an Effective and Efficient Curriculum*. California: SAGE Publications.
21. Shen, A. C. (2009). *HRM Strategic Integration and Organizational Performance*. California: SAGE Publications Ltd.
22. SRINIVASAN, R. (2014). *STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT: THE INDIAN CONTEXT*. New Delhi: PHI Learning Pvt. Ltd.
23. Tan, Albert Wee Kwan, Theodorou, Petros. (2009). *Strategic Information Technology and Portfolio Management*. Pennsylvania: IGI Global.
24. Trivedi, J. H. (2019). *Fundamentals Of Strategic Planning And Development*. Navamuvada: Red Unicorn Publishing Pvt, Ltd.

Cite this article:

Al-Mafrachi, mustafa saad, Aboura, Enas Hussein & Abed, Hanaa Najm (2021). Strategic Management of Human Resources in light of Technological changes. *International Journal of Science and Business*, 5(8), 278-288. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5115472>

Retrieved from <http://ijsab.com/wp-content/uploads/798.pdf>

Published by

